

ReBioCycle Project Key Messages

1 Comprehensive Solutions for Bioplastics Recycling

The ReBioCycle project provides a portfolio of advanced sorting, innovative pre-treatment and recycling technologies tailored to bioplastics, focusing on PLA, PHA, and composites.

Three main recycling technologies will be demonstrated at pilot and demonstration scale, delivering high-quality recycled polymers:

- Mechanical recycling
- Chemical Recycling
- Biological recycling, done with enzymes and with microorganisms.

2 Scalable Recycling Technologies tested in Specialised Hubs

ReBioCycle operates through three specialised hubs located in Europe. The hubs ensure compatibility with existing waste management systems and optimise collection and sorting for biodegradable bioplastics. The hubs scale up their technologies from pilot to demonstration scale.

Dutch HUB

Spanish HUB

Italian HUB

The Dutch Hub uses chemical recycling (TORWASH technology) to transform PLA and PHA into rPLA and PHBV.

The Spanish Hub uses enzymatic and microbial recycling to achieve rPLA and rPHA.

The Italian Hub uses chemical recycling to transform mixed composites into rComposites with 15% recycled content. It also receives rPHA from the Dutch and Spanish Hubs to create new bioplastic formulations.

Pilot scale: A small-scale version of the technology designed to test its performance and feasibility in a real-world environment, but on a limited or smaller scale compared to full commercial production

Demonstration scale: A larger-scale test that aims to show the technology can be used successfully in an industrial or commercial setting. The goal here is not just to test the concept, but to demonstrate that it can operate effectively at a scale closer to commercial deployment.

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3 Delivery of High-Quality, Market-Ready Recycled Bioplastics

ReBioCycle targets producing recycled materials that match the same grade as virgin products, including food-grade plastics.

Outputs of the recycling processes will also be upgraded for higher-value applications, with real-world demonstrations of durable and multi-use packaging by brand owners such as ARAPAHA, based on PLA, and Sulapac, based on PHA and composites.

credits: Sulapac

ReBioCycle enables biobased polymers' providers to integrate their products into new value chains, opening market expansion opportunities.

4 Applications in Packaging and Durable Goods

ReBioCycle targets two key sectors where biobased biodegradable plastics can improve end-of-life options:

- **Packaging** focusing on non-single-use items and compostable packaging solutions to enhance sustainability.
- **Durable goods** including textiles and injection-moulded products to promote recycled bioplastics and recyclability enhancement.

credits: DRAAG bag by ARAPAHA

credits: Novamont

Curious to learn more? Get in touch with us!

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